

Instrument Catalogue of Small–Sized Bassoons, ca. 1700–ca. 1915

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The catalogue of small bassoons presented here constitutes the core of the research about these instruments. It represents all the evidence gathered by the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis research team in the years 2017 to 2023 regarding surviving fagottini and tenoroons from ca. 1700 to 1915.¹

About half of the preserved instruments were examined and measured *in situ* by members of the team. Initially, only these instruments were given FT-numbers (FT = Fagottino/Tenoroon), up to FT61. The order of the numbers is random, depending on the initial information received; these instruments are marked “examined” in the catalogue. Detailed datasets of examined instruments can be found online (see below). Instruments from unknown makers are noted as “Anonymous”, with consecutive numbering (Anonymous 1, Anonymous 2, etc.).

During the preparation of this publication, it was decided to assign an FT number to all other instruments in order to make them clearly identifiable in future research and publications. Additionally, there are a few instruments and records that either fall outside the time frame or do not meet the design criteria of the objects studied. These are listed with "M" numbers (for “miscellaneous”). A total of 136 instruments, made over a period of about 200 years, have been documented.

For reasons of clarity, bibliographic references are abbreviated in the catalogue entries, where it was also considered useful to include brief notes about some instruments. A list of complete references can be found in Section III.

In addition to the catalogue, an alphabetical list of makers is given so that small bassoons by a particular maker can be identified quickly. Further information can be found in the main catalogue via the FT number.

Detailed datasets (dimensions, comments, photos, videos) of the instruments marked “examined” (FT1–FT61, M2, M3) are available online and publicly accessible in two digital repositories; only the permalinks for the “Zenodo” platform are provided in the catalogue entries. Identical datasets about individual instruments, and the full

¹ Status of the catalogue: October 2024

documentation of the research project, can be found at the repository DaSCH:
<https://www.dasch.swiss/project/fagottini-and-tenoroons%3A-small-sized-bassoons-from-the-18th-and-19th-centuries>.

In the digital version of this publication, the links are active and lead directly to the corresponding websites.

I. Main Catalogue (ordered by ID-numbers)

FT1

Maker: ADLER, Frédéric G.
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1835
Location: Boston/MA (US), Boston Symphony Orchestra Collection (Casadesus collection), Casadesus Collection #65
Reference/Notes: De Wolfe Howe, Casadesus (1931), 263
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 328
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 3
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2647780>

FT2

Maker: ADLER, Frédéric G.
Instrument: 13-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1840
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la Philharmonie de Paris E.2463
Reference/Notes: Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 713
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237813>

FT3

Maker: ANONYMOUS 1
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: [Unknown], ca. 1820–1850
Location: Italy, private collection
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2647807>

FT4

Maker: ANONYMOUS 4
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: [Germany], ca. 1780
Location: Amsterdam (NL), private collection
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7837280>

FT5

Maker: SCHUBERT, Louis-Paul (formerly listed as “Anonymous 6”)
Instrument: 13-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1860
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la Philharmonie de Paris E.971.7.2
Reference/Notes: Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 722
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648160>

FT6

Maker: ANONYMOUS 7
Instrument: 8-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: [Vienna/Naples], ca. 1815
Location: Switzerland, private collection
Reference/Notes: Viennese key system; was recovered in Italy
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3526420>

FT7

Maker: ANONYMOUS 8
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: [Germany], ca. 1730–1770
Location: Stockholm (SE), Scenkonstmuseet
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269294>

FT8

Maker: ASTOR, Georg & HORWOOD
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [F?]; examined
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1815
Location: Greenville/SC (US), Sigal Music Museum 1995.28
Reference/Notes: Rice, Four Centuries (2015), 173
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269188>

FT9

Maker: BLOCKLEY, John
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Ullesthorpe/Leicestershire (UK), ca. 1780
Location: Boston/MA (US), Museum of Fine Arts, 17.1923
Reference/Notes: Bessaraboff, Musical instruments (1941), 132
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 339
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 35
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648178>

FT10

Maker: BONACCORSI
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Barga (IT), ca. 1815
Location: Stockholm (SE), Nydahl Collection ITBO86
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 39
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269329>

FT11

Maker: CAHUSAC, Thomas 1
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]; examined
Provenance/Date: London, 1789
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de Musique 996
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, Catalogue Bruxelles (1893/1978), Vol. II, 268
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 55
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 45
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269319>

FT12

Maker: CASTLAS
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Turin, ca. 1800
Location: Paris (FR), Bruno Kampmann collection BK 44
Reference/Notes: Kampmann (1986), 53
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269411>

FT13

Maker: DELUSSE, Christophe
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1783
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la Philharmonie de Paris E.255 C.499
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 354
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 85
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 55
Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 650
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3270809>

FT14

Maker: DENNER, Johann C.
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave; examined

Provenance/Date: Nuremberg, ca. 1700
Location: Boston/MA (US), Museum of Fine Arts 17.1922
Reference/Notes: Bessaraboff, Musical instruments (1941), 132
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 85
Kuronen, Musical Instruments (2013), 66
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246244>

FT15

Maker: GRENSER, Heinrich & WIESNER, Samuel
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Dresden, ca. 1824
Location: Stockholm (SE), Scenkonstmuseet M3331
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 383
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 146
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 108
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269762>

FT16

Maker: GRENSER, Heinrich
Instrument: 5-key fagottino / octave; examined by 3rd
parties
Provenance/Date: Dresden, ca. 1800
Location: The Hague (NL), Gemeentemuseum
Ea.402.1933
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 383
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 105
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699966>

FT17

Maker: JACOBY Fils
Instrument: 5-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Auch, ca. 1785
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.2479
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 191
Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 713
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3267140>

FT18

Maker: KRAUS, I.
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1775
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.750
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 215

Online: Gétreau, *Aux origines* (1996), 667
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3266438>

FT19

Maker: MERKLEIN, I.
Instrument: 8-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1835
Location: Vicenza (IT), private collection
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3280189>

FT20

Maker: MÜLLER
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1770
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 992
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, *Catalogue Bruxelles* (1893/1978),
Vol. 2, 265
Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 447
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 274
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3293927>

FT21

Maker: PORTHAUX, Dominique A.
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1808
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.971.7.1
Reference/Notes: Gétreau, *Aux origines* (1996), 722
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3267389>

FT22

Maker: PROFF, François X.
Instrument: 5-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Tours, ca. 1800
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.2190
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 311
Gétreau, *Aux origines* (1996), 707
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3336607>

FT23

Maker: ROTTENBURGH, Godfrigus A.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Brussels, ca. 1760
Location: Greenville/SC (US), Sigal Music Museum
1983.13
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 192
Rice, Four Centuries (2015), 171
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3267160>

FT24

Maker: SAVARY PERE
Instrument: 5-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1810
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.2189
Reference/Notes: Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 707
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3270534>

FT25

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 13-key fagottino / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1827
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.646 C.500
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 472
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 199
Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 709
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3241877>

FT26

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1838
Location: Europe, private collection
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699743>

FT27

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 16-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1841
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.2329
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 199
Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 709

Online: Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3301458>

FT28

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1760
Location: Paris (FR), Le Musée de la musique de la
Philharmonie de Paris E.186 C.498
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 210
Gétreau, Aux origines (1996), 664
Domínguez, Fagottini (2019), 6–19
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3276353>

FT29

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1764
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 426
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, Catalogue Bruxelles (1893/1978),
Vol. 1, 436–437
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 478
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 210
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3241603>

FT30

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 5-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1760–1778
Location: Zurich (CH), Museum für Gestaltung 1963-
60.102
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 478
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 353
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 210
Formerly in Museum Bellerive Zurich
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3241608>

FT31

Maker: TAUBER, Kaspar
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]; examined
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1815
Location: Greenville/SC (US), Sigal Music Museum
2007.15
Reference/Notes: Rice, Four Centuries (2015), 173

Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2652907>

FT32

Maker: TÖLCKE, Heinrich Carl
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Braunschweig, ca. 1780
Location: Meiningen (DE), Musiksammlung M62
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 401
Goltz, Meininger Museen (2012), 194–197

FT33

Maker: TUERLINCKX, Jean A.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Mechelen (Belgium), ca. 1795
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 185
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, Catalogue Bruxelles (1893/1978),
Vol. 1. 238
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 511
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 246
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2639507>

FT34

Maker: TUERLINCKX, Jean A.
Instrument: 5-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Mechelen (BE), ca. 1820
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 184
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, Catalogue Bruxelles (1893/1978),
Vol. 1, 238
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 246
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3311608>

FT35

Maker: DUPRÉ, Joseph
Instrument: 0-key unfinished fagottino; examined
Provenance/Date: Tournai (Belgium), ca. 1820–1850
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 2627/JR0060
Reference/Notes: Mahillon, Catalogue Bruxelles (1893/1978),
Vol. 4, 363
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 362
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648191>

FT36

Maker: GAUTROT Aîné
Instrument: 16-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1845–84
Location: UK, Waterhouse collection 63.3
Reference/Notes: Kopp, *The Bassoon* (2012), 226
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3311979>

FT37

Maker: MARZOLI, A.G. Philippe / Tribert Marzoli
Boehm (TMB)
Instrument: 15-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1860
Location: UK, Waterhouse collection 58.2
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 437
Waterhouse, *Proud Bassoon* (1983), Cat. entry 33.
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 153
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3329023>

FT38

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1842
Location: UK, Waterhouse collection 79.3
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, *Proud Bassoon* (1983), Cat. entry 32
Young, *Loan Exhibition* (1988), Cat. entry 74
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 246
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3241731>

FT39

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1750–1778
Location: UK, Waterhouse collection 7.3
Reference/Notes: *Made for Music* (1986), Cat. entry 81
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 210
Formerly in Galpin Society Collection
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3294589>

FT40

Maker: ANONYMOUS 11
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: [Unknown], ca. 1750–90
Location: Switzerland, private collection
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831175>

FT41

Maker: HIRSBRUNNER (Gebrüder)
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Sumiswald (CH), ca. 1830
Location: Berne (CH), Klingende Sammlung 1919
Reference/Notes: von Steiger, Hirsbrunner (2016), 196
Former Hirsbrunner family collection
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3294454>

FT42

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1840
Location: Switzerland, private collection
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831175>

FT43

Maker: LEIBERZ, Johann Peter
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Koblenz, ca. 1825–1835
Location: Leipzig (DE), Museum für Musikinstrumente
der Universität Leipzig 1362
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1; 429, Vol.
5: Plate 15, Fig. 40
Heyde, *Rohrblattinstrumente Leipzig* (1979),
412–414
Heyde, *Über Rohrblattinstrumente* (1979), 383
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 231
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246266>

FT44

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1760–1770
Location: Leipzig (DE), Museum für Musikinstrumente
der Universität Leipzig 1548
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 478
Young, *Loan Exhibition* (1988), Cat. entry 54
Heyde, *Rohrblattinstrumente Leipzig* (1979),
414–415
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 210
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246272>

FT45

Maker: STEHLE, Johann
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1850–1860
Location: Leipzig (DE), Museum für Musikinstrumente
der Universität Leipzig 1365
Reference/Notes: Heyde, Rohrblattinstrumente Leipzig (1979),
418–419
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 384
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246282>

FT46

Maker: ANONYMOUS 12
Instrument: 5-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: [Germany], ca. 1815
Location: Leipzig (DE), Museum für Musikinstrumente
der Universität Leipzig 1363
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 5, Plate 15,
Fig. 39
Heyde, Rohrblattinstrumente Leipzig (1979),
415–416
Kinsky, Heyer (ca. 1914), 175–176
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3311760>

FT47

Maker: RIVA, Giacinto
Instrument: 13-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Ferrara, ca. 1860–1870
Location: Leipzig (DE), Museum für Musikinstrumente
der Universität Leipzig 1364
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 330
Online: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246324>

FT48

Maker: TAUBER, Kaspar
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon; examined
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1820–1829
Location: Trieste (IT), Civico Museo Teatrale Carlo
Schmidl 991
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699642>

FT49

Maker: KÜSS, Wolfgang
Instrument: 10-key tenoroon; examined
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1810–1839
Location: Italy, private collection
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978) Vol. 3, 422

Online: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 142
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4460187>

FT50

Maker: GRENSER, Heinrich
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Dresden, ca. 1806–1813
Location: Berlin (DE), Musikinstrumenten Museum.
Staatliches Institut für Musikforschung 2973
Reference/Notes: Otto, MIM Berlin (1965), 69
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 105
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4308926>

FT51

Maker: ANONYMOUS 3
Instrument: 10-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1830
Location: London (UK), Horniman Museum 2004.1044
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698459>

FT52

Maker: ANONYMOUS 9
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1800–1825
Location: London (UK), Horniman Museum 14.5.47/278
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.769848>

FT53

Maker: PACE, Charles
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1825
Location: London (UK), Horniman Museum 2004.1068
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698504>

FT54

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 14-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1845–1850
Location: London (UK), Horniman Museum 1976.224
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698522>

FT55

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 10-key tenoroon / F; examined

Provenance/Date: Paris, 1835
Location: London (UK), Royal College of Music Museum
RCM 0998
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698547>

FT56

Maker: BÜHNER & KELLER
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Strasbourg, ca. 1810
Location: London (UK), Royal College of Music Museum
RCM 0089
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 346
Ridley, *The Royal College* (1982), 28
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 41
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698923>

FT57

Maker: MILHOUSE, William
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / [G?]; examined
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1800
Location: London (UK), Royal College of Music Museum
RCM 0442
Reference/Notes: Ridley, *The Royal College* (1982), 18–19
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698937>

FT58

Maker: SAXTON, Thomas
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Nottingham, 1793–1799
Location: London (UK), Royal College of Music Museum
RCM0225
Reference/Notes: Ridley, *The Royal College* (1982), 28
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698967>

FT59

Maker: KUTERUF, J.
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave; examined
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1700–1760
Location: Munich (DE), Deutsches Museum 21641
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 422
Seifers, *Blasinstrumente München* (1980), 69
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 219
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698983>

FT60

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / G; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1824
Location: Switzerland, private collection
Reference/Notes: Formerly in the Richard W. and Jeannine E. Abel Musical Instrument Collection; acquired from Tony Bingham, London, 1996.
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782327>

FT61

Maker: ADLER, Frédéric G.
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / F; examined
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1840
Location: Switzerland, private collection
Reference/Notes: Formerly in the Richard W. and Jeannine E. Abel Musical Instrument Collection; acquired from Tony Bingham, London, 1996
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831952>

FT62

Maker: ANONYMOUS 2
Instrument: x-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: [Unknown], ca. 1830
Location: Nice (FR), Musée du Palais Lascaris C.152
Online: <http://basenationale.philharmoniedeparis.fr/doc/BASENATIONALE /0875954/basson-quinte-tenoron-en-sol>

FT63

Maker: ANONYMOUS 5
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1800
Location: Formerly in Henk de Wit collection
Reference/Notes: Langeveld, Tentoonstelling (1992), #39

FT64

Maker: ANONYMOUS 10
Instrument: 7-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: [France], ca. 1850–1898
Location: Madrid (ES), Patrimonio Nacional, Palacio Real
Reference/Notes: Bordas, Instrumentos musicales (2008), Vol. II, 66

FT65

Maker: ANONYMOUS 13
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: [France], ca. 1700–1780
Location: New York (US), Metropolitan Museum of Art
89.4.2037
Reference/Notes: Crosby Brown, Collection (1904), Vol. I, 149, ill.
Online: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/502615>

FT66

Maker: ANONYMOUS 14
Instrument: 10-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1820
Location: New York (US), Metropolitan Museum of Art
89.4.2202
Reference/Notes: Crosby Brown, Collection (1904), Vol. I, 149, ill.
Online: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/503867>

FT67

Maker: ANONYMOUS 15
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1800
Location: Tucson/AZ, (US), private collection

FT68

Maker: ANONYMOUS 16
Instrument: 14-key tenoroon / [F?]
Provenance/Date: [Germany], ca. 1825–1850
Location: Stuttgart (DE), private collection
Reference/Notes: See similarities to FT41

FT69

Maker: ANONYMOUS 17
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: [United Kingdom], ca. 1800
Location: British Columbia (CA), Instrument dealer
Online: <http://www.music-treasures.com/antwood.htm>

FT70

Maker: ANONYMOUS 18
Instrument: 0-key unfinished fagottino

Provenance/Date: [Unknown], ca. 1820
Location: Linz (AT), Oberösterreichsches Landesmuseum
Formerly Kremsmünster (AT), Musikinstrumenten-Museum Schloss Kremsegg, 84-7-54
Formerly in Streitwieser Foundation, Pottstown/PA (US), (Ex-Sarah Frishmuth Collection)
Reference/Notes: Examined in April 2019 by Michael Söllner

FT71

Maker: ANONYMOUS 19
Instrument: 13-key tenoroon / G
Provenance/Date: [France], 1860–1870
Location: France, collection of Thibouville/Cambouville (THI/CAM)

FT72

Maker: BABB, G.
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1780
Location: Oxford (UK), Bate Collection of Musical Instruments x34
Reference/Notes: Baines, The Bate Collection (1976), 29
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 332
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 14

Online:

<http://minim.ac.uk/index.php/explore/?instrument=3921>

FT73

Maker: BLOCKLEY, John
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: Ullesthorpe/ Leicestershire (UK), ca. 1760–1798
Location: UK (?), Formerly (ca. 1978) in private collection Wolverhampton, UK

FT74

Maker: BOOSEY & Co.
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: London, 1899
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Boosey & Hawkes Archive. B&Co. Instruments Wood 3 (1896–1904). HM/B&H A227/015

FT75

Maker: BOOSEY & Co.
Instrument: 10-key tenoroon / [F?]
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1880
Location: [London (UK), Horniman Museum]
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 340
The instrument was not located in the Museum,
(11/2022)

FT76

Maker: BUFFET-CRAMPON
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1900
Location: Leeds (UK), City Museum
Reference/Notes: Langwill, *Bassoon* (1948), 36

FT77

Maker: CAHUSAC, Thomas
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: London, 1788
Location: Halifax (UK), Bankfield Museum MI 37
Byrne, *The Church Band* (1964), 95
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 347
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 45

FT78

Maker: COLLINGS, Joseph
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: United Kingdom, ca. 1771–1773
Location: Formerly in Frank Rendell collection
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 69

FT79

Maker: CUSTODE, Cristofaro
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Naples, ca. 1800–1830
Location: Rome (IT), Museo Nazionale degli Strumenti
Musicali 773 / 231
Reference/Notes: Cervelli, *Galleria Armonica* (1994)

FT80

Maker: DE ROSA, R.
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / G

Provenance/Date: Naples, ca. 1835
Location: London (UK), Victoria & Albert Museum 46–1884
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol 1, 466
Baines, *V & A Museum* (1998), 98
Online: <https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O249372/tenoroon-de-rosa-r/>

FT81

Maker: EICHENTOPF, Johann H.
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1740
Location: Halle (DE), Händel-Haus
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 365
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 69
Heyde, *Händel-Haus Halle* (1980), 276–277

FT82

Maker: EISENBRANDT, Johann Benjamin
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Göttingen, ca. 1785–1822
Location: Berlin (DE), Musikinstrumenten Museum, Staatliches Institut für Musikforschung 2972
Reference/Notes: Otto, *MIM Berlin* (1965), 69

FT83

Maker: EVETTE & SCHAEFFER
Instrument: 17-key tenoroons / Eb, F, G
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1889 & 1912
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Pierre, *La facture* (1890), 26–28
Evette & Schaeffer (1912), 21–25
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 104
Presented in the Exposition Universelle Paris 1889

FT84

Maker: GEROCK, Christopher
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1804–1837
Location: St. Petersburg (RU), Muzei Muzikalnich Instrumentov Teatra, Muziki, I Kinematografii 527
Reference/Notes: Kopp, *The Bassoon* (2012), 226

FT85

Maker: GOULDING, PHIPPS, AND D'ALMAINE
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: London, 1785–1834
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Lasocki, *New Light* (2010), 129

FT86

Maker: GRENSER, Augustin
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Dresden, ca. 1744–1798
Location: Copenhagen (DK), Musikmuseet (Carl Claudius Samling) E.140
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 382
Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 113

FT87

Maker: GRENSER, Heinrich
Instrument: 5-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Dresden, ca. 1796–1813
Location: Frankfurt am Main (DE), Historisches Museum X26.469
Reference/Notes: Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 105

FT88

Maker: HECKEL, Wilhelm
Instrument: 18-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Biebrich, 1907
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Heckel, *Verzeichnis* (ca. 1907), 7
Kopp, *The Bassoon* (2012), 227

FT89

Maker: HIRSBRUNNER (Gebrüder)
Instrument: 6-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Sumiswald (CH), ca. 1815–1848
Location: Lucerne (CH), Haus der Musik 134
Reference/Notes: von Steiger, *Hirsbrunner* (2016), 181–200:196

FT90

Maker: KEY, Thomas
Instrument: x-key fagottino
Provenance/Date: London (UK), ca. 1805–1858
Location: Formerly in Rudall Carte collection

Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 204

FT91

Maker: KRAUS, I.
Instrument: 3-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1750–1790
Location: Munich (DE), Musikinstrumentenmuseum im Münchner Stadtmuseum Mu 120
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 141

FT92

Maker: KRAUS, I.
Instrument: 3-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1750–1790
Location: Hamamatsu-city (JP), Hamamatsu Museum of Musical Instruments A-02I3R
Reference/Notes: Young, The Look of Music (1980), 98
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 141
Formerly in Rosenbaum Collection

FT93

Maker: KRAUS, I.
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1750–1790
Location: Salzburg (AT), Salzburg Museum (formerly: Museum Carolino Augusteum) Car-Aug 15/7
Reference/Notes: Birsak, Salzburg (1973), 40
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 141

FT94

Maker: KRAUS, I.
Instrument: 4-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1750–1790
Location: Eisenach (DE), Historische Musikinstrumente im Bachhaus I-158
Reference/Notes: Heyde, Bachhaus Eisenach (1976)
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 418
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 141

FT95

Maker: KÜSS, Wolfgang
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1810–1839
Location: Biebrich (DE), Heckel Museum PF-2
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 218

FT96

Maker: KÜSS, Wolfgang
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1810–1840
Location: Prague (CZ), Národní muzeum, Czech museum of music 12 /102
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 412

FT97

Maker: LE BRETON
Instrument: Small-size bassoon referred to as “counter-tenor basson”
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1692
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, *New Langwill* (1993), 228
Kopp, *The Bassoon* (2012), 223

FT98

Maker: LOT, Martin
Instrument: 5-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1743–1785
Location: Oxford (UK), Bate Collection of Musical Instruments 334
Reference/Notes: Baines, *The Bate Collection* (1976), 29
Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 434
Young, *4900 Instruments* (1993), 149

FT99

Maker: LOT, Martin
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1743–1786
Location: London (UK), Royal College of Music (Donaldson Collection)
Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 434
Matei, *Peculiarities* (2001), 75

FT100

Maker: MAGVINI (MAGRINI)
Instrument: 8-key tenoroon / [F?]
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1800
Location: Kronach (DE), Collection of Guntram Wolf
Reference/Notes: Hubmann, *Hochgestimmte Fagotte* (2011), 83

FT101

Maker: MILHOUSE, William
Instrument: 8-key tenoroon / G
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1799–1828
Location: Vermillion/SD (US), National Music Museum
NMM 2671
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 163
Online:

<https://emuseum.nmmusd.org/objects/5953/tenor-bassoon?ctx=f29b325f-bdf0-4f05-bed9-85760d6a2d1b&idx=21>

FT102

Maker: MILHOUSE, William
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1800
Location: Tucson/AZ, (US), private collection

FT103

Maker: MORTON, Alfred W.
Instrument: 15-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1870
Location: Hamamatsu-city (JP), Hamamatsu Museum of Musical Instruments
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 273
Formerly in Rosenbaum Collection

FT104

Maker: PEALE, T.
Instrument: 7-key tenoroon / [G?]
Provenance/Date: United Kingdom, ca. 1870
Location: Oxford (UK), Bate Collection of Musical Instruments 335
Reference/Notes: Baines, The Bate Collection (1976), 2
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 459
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 294

Online:

<http://minim.ac.uk/index.php/explore/?instrument=3922>

FT105

Maker: PELITTI
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Milan, ca. 1828–1870
Location: Formerly in John B. Taylor Instrument Collection (1875-1963), Williamstown, MA (US)

Reference/Notes: Kopp, The Bassoon (2012), 226

FT106

Maker: PRUDENT [Thierriot]
Instrument: x-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1765–1783
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference]
Reference/Notes: Jeltsch, Prudent (1997), 151
Postmortum inventory of Prudent included several octave bassoons.

FT107

Maker: ROTTENBURGH, Godfrius A.
Instrument: x-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Brussels, ca. 1760
Location: Former collection J.-A. Stellfeld olim 1100
Baeck-Schilders, Bibliotheca Stellfeldiana (2004), 203–223
Reference/Notes: The collection catalogue entry mentioned in this reference states: “1100. Basson piccolo. En acajou fonce. Marque C.A., a Rottenburg”.

FT108

Maker: ROTTENBURGH, Godfrius A.
Instrument: x-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Brussels, ca. 1760
Location: Former collection J.-A. Stellfeld olim 1100
Baeck-Schilders, Bibliotheca Stellfeldiana (2004), 203–223
Reference/Notes: The collection catalogue entry mentioned in this reference states: “1102. Basson piccolo. En acajou fonce. Marque C.A., a Rottenburg”.

FT109

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 14-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1840
Location: Edinburgh (UK), University of Edinburgh 169
Reference/Notes: Myers, Edinburgh Univ. Collection (1993), 9
Online: <https://collections.ed.ac.uk/mimed/record/15952>
<https://collections.ed.ac.uk/stcecilias/record/95854>

FT110

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1843
Location: Private collection AVB-990
Online: <http://instrumantiq.com/images/AVB/AVB-990-basson-Savary-Jeune.jpg>

FT111

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 11-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1832
Location: Biebrich (DE), Heckel Museum PF-1
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 199

FT112

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 15-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1840
Location: Oxford (UK), Bate Collection of Musical Instruments 336
Reference/Notes: Baines, The Bate Collection (1976), 29
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 472

FT113

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: 15-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, ca. 1835–1850
Location: Perth, (AU)
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 199
Formerly in Bate Collection (337), Oxford (UK)

FT114

Maker: SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas
Instrument: x-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Paris, 1842
Location: North Carolina, USA, Private collection

FT115

Maker: SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Butzbach, ca. 1750–1778
Location: Kassel (DE), Mollenhauer (instrument makers collection)

FT116

Maker: SCHLEGEL, Jeremias
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Basel, ca. 1752–1792
Location: Copenhagen (DK), Musikmuseet (Carl Claudius Samling) E.132
Reference/Notes: Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 213

FT117

Maker: SCHOLL, Franz
Instrument: x-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Vienna, 1803
Location: [Unknown, historical catalogue reference 1803]
Reference/Notes: Kopp, The Bassoon (2012), 225
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 361

FT118

Maker: SCHRAMME, C.
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Germany, ca. 1700–1740
Location: Prague (CZ), Národní muzeum, Czech museum of music E. 1374
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 362

FT119

Maker: SCHUSTER, Gottfried
Instrument: 6-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Markneukirchen, ca. 1820
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 482
Location: Markneukirchen (DE), Musikinstrumenten-Museum Markneukirchen 0105

FT120

Maker: SPADA, Gaetano
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Bologna, 1873
Reference/Notes: de Castrone-Marchesi, Relazioni (1873), 55

FT121

Maker: TAUBER, Kaspar
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1798–1829
Location: Salzburg (AT), Salzburg Museum (formerly: Museum Carolino Augusteum) Car-Aug 15/8

Reference/Notes: Birsak, Salzburg (1973), 40
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 395
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 235

FT122

Maker: TAUBER, Kaspar
Instrument: 12-key tenoroon / F
Provenance/Date: Vienna, ca. 1798–1829
Location: Berlin (DE), Musikinstrumenten Museum.
Staatliches Institut für Musikforschung 1873
Reference/Notes: Otto, MIM Berlin (1965), 69
Young, 4900 Instruments (1993), 235

FT123

Maker: TÖLCKE, Heinrich Carl
Instrument: 4-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: Braunschweig, ca. 1770–1780
Location: Eisenach (DE), Bachhaus I 157
Reference/Notes: Heyde, Bachhaus Eisenach (1976), 238
Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 506
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 401

FT124

Maker: TREUMANN
Instrument: x-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Lyon, ca. 1825–1850
Location: Paris (FR)
Reference/Notes: Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 403
Formerly in La Collection Musicale de
Geneviève Thibault

FT125

Maker: WUSSINGER, Franz
Instrument: 9-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: Klagenfurt, ca. 1810–1841
Location: Wien (AT), Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde (on
deposit at Kunsthistorisches Museum)
Reference/Notes: Mandyczewski, Zusatz-Band (1912), 170
Waterhouse, New Langwill (1993), 438

FT126

Maker: MORTON & SONS, also stamped JOHN
PARR
Instrument: 16-key tenoroon
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1880–1890

Location: Formerly in the late John Parr Collection,
Sheffield (UK),
Reference/Notes: Lindstead, John Parr (1945), 172
UK auction 8 December 2023
https://www.the-saleroom.com/en-gb/auction-catalogues/gardiner-houlgate/catalogue-id-srgard10258/lot-179b1144-7388-49ac-b1be-b0bb00caefa9?utm_source=auction-alert&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=auction-alert&utm_content=lot-view-link&queryId=8243d1ffcce60e88f27cbac55382e1a3
(29 January 2024)

MISCELLANEOUS SMALL-SIZED INSTRUMENTS

M1

Maker: ANONYMOUS 20
Instrument: 3-key fagottino / octave
Provenance/Date: [Unknown]
Reference/Notes: 20th century copy
Location: Amsterdam (NL), private collection

M2

Maker: WOOD, Georg
Instrument: 7-key alto fagotto; examined
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1835
Location: Brussels (BE), Musée des Instruments de
Musique 944
Reference/Notes: Hybrid instrument with clarinet-like mouthpiece
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2649457>

M3

Maker: WOOD, Georg & IVY
Instrument: 8-key alto fagotto, examined
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1840
Location: Boston/MA (US), Museum of Fine Arts 17.189
Reference/Notes: Illustrated Catalogue Music Loan (1909), 192
Hybrid instrument with clarinet-like mouthpiece
Online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2649035>

M4

Maker: FORNIARI, Andrea
Instrument: Experimental instrument similar to baritone
oboe
Provenance/Date: Venice, ca. 1800–1832

Location: Milan (IT), Conservatorio "Giuseppe Verdi"

M5

Maker: HAWKES & SON
Instrument: 12-key fagottino
Provenance/Date: London, 1923
Location: Oxford (UK), Bate Collection of Musical Instruments 333

M6

Maker: HAWKES & SON
Instrument: 12-key fagottino
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1925
Location: Brighton (UK), Albert C. Spencer Collection, Royal Pavillion and Museums Brighton MS100158

M7

Maker: MEIKLE, William
Instrument: 8-key caledonica
Provenance/Date: Strathaven, 1820s
Location: Edinburgh (UK), University of Edinburgh
Reference/Notes: Marcuse, Musical Instruments (1964), 12
Conical instrument invented by Meikle with bassoon shape, played with a clarinet-like mouthpiece.

M8

Maker: PIATET & BENOIT
Instrument: x-key alto fagotto
Provenance/Date: Lyon, ca. 1850
Location: Formerly in the late John Parr Collection, Sheffield (UK)
Reference/Notes: Jansen, The Bassoon (1978), Vol. 1, 452
Hybrid instrument with clarinet-like mouthpiece

M9

Maker: [WOOD, George & IVY, unstamped]
Instrument: 7-key alto fagotto
Provenance/Date: London, ca. 1830
Location: London (UK), Victoria and Albert Museum 47-1884
Reference/Notes: Baines, V & A Museum (1998), 99
Hybrid instrument with a clarinet-like mouthpiece

M10

Maker: MILHOUSE, William and KEY, T.
 Instrument: 8-key tenoroon
 Provenance: London, ca. 1795–1820
 Location: Cardiff (UK), Amgueddfa Cymru – Museum Wales 32.440
 Reference/Notes: Jansen, *The Bassoon* (1978), Vol. 1, 440
 Ivory mouthpiece for a single reed

II. Short List in Alphabetical Order of Makers

ID NR	MAKER	INSTRUMENT	PROVENANCE/DATE
FT1	ADLER, Frédéric G.	11-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1835
FT2	ADLER, Frédéric G.	13-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1840
FT61	ADLER, Frédéric G.	11-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1840
FT3	ANONYMOUS 1	4-key fagottino / octave	ca. 1820–1850
FT62	ANONYMOUS 2	x-key tenoroon / F	ca. 1830
FT51	ANONYMOUS 3	10-key tenoroon / F	[United Kingdom], ca. 1830
FT4	ANONYMOUS 4	4-key fagottino / octave	[Germany], ca. 1780
FT63	ANONYMOUS 5	6-key fagottino / octave	[United Kingdom], ca. 1800
FT6	ANONYMOUS 7	8-key tenoroon / G	[Vienna/Naples], ca. 1815
FT7	ANONYMOUS 8	3-key fagottino / octave	[Germany], ca. 1730–1770
FT52	ANONYMOUS 9	6-key fagottino / octave	[United Kingdom] ca. 1800–1825
FT64	ANONYMOUS 10	7-key fagottino / octave	[France], ca. 1850–1898
FT40	ANONYMOUS 11	4-key fagottino / octave	ca. 1750–1790
FT46	ANONYMOUS 12	5-key tenoroon / G	[Germany], ca. 1815
FT65	ANONYMOUS 13	3-key fagottino / octave	[France], ca. 1700–1780
FT66	ANONYMOUS 14	10-key tenoroon / F	[United Kingdom], ca. 1820
FT67	ANONYMOUS 15	6-key tenoroon / [G?]	[United Kingdom], ca. 1800
FT68	ANONYMOUS 16	14-key tenoroon / [F?]	[Germany], ca. 1825–1850
FT69	ANONYMOUS 17	6-key tenoroon / F	[United Kingdom], ca. 1800

FT70	ANONYMOUS 18	0-key unfinished fagottino	ca. 1820
FT71	ANONYMOUS 19	13-key tenoroon / G	[France], 1860–1870
M1	ANONYMOUS 20	3-key fagottino / octave	20th century copy
FT8	ASTOR, Georg & HORWOOD	6-key tenoroon / [F?]	London, ca. 1815
FT72	BABB, G.	6-key tenoroon / [G?]	London, ca. 1780
FT9	BLOCKLEY, John	4-key tenoroon / G	Ullesthorpe, ca. 1780
FT73	BLOCKLEY, John	6-key tenoroon / [G?]	Ullesthorpe, ca. 1760–1798
FT10	BONACCORSI	7-key fagottino / octave	Barga, ca. 1815
FT74	BOOSEY & Co.	x-key tenoroon	London, 1899
FT75	BOOSEY & Co.	10-key tenoroon / [F?]	London, ca. 1880
FT76	BUFFET-CRAMPON	x-key tenoroon	Paris, ca. 1900
FT56	BÜHNER & KELLER	7-key fagottino / octave	Strasbourg, ca. 1810
FT11	CAHUSAC, Thomas	6-key tenoroon / [G?]	London, 1789
FT77	CAHUSAC, Thomas	4-key tenoroon	London, ca. 1788
FT12	CASTLAS	7-key fagottino / octave	Turin, ca. 1800
FT78	COLLINGS, Joseph	3-key fagottino / octave	United Kingdom, ca. 1771– 1773
FT79	CUSTODE, Cristofaro	4-key fagottino / octave	Naples, ca. 1800–1830
FT80	DE ROSA, R.	11-key tenoroon / G	Naples, ca. 1830
FT13	DELUSSE, Christophe	7-key fagottino / octave	Paris, ca. 1783
FT14	DENNER, Johann C.	3-key fagottino / octave	Nuremberg, ca. 1700
FT35	DUPRÉ, Joseph	0-key unfinished fagottino	Tournai, ca. 1820–1850
FT81	EICHENTOPF, Johann H.	3-key fagottino / octave	Germany, ca. 1740
FT82	EISENBRANDT, Johann Benjamin	x-key tenoroon	Göttingen, ca. 1785–1822
FT83	EVETTE & SCHAEFFER	17-key tenoroons / Eb, F, G	Paris, 1889 & 1912
M4	FORNIARI, Andrea	Experimental instrument similar to baritone oboe	Venice, ca. 1800–1832
FT36	GAUTROT Aîné	16-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1845–1884
FT84	GEROCK, Christopher	x-key tenoroon	London, ca. 1804–1837

FT85	GOULDING, PHIPPS, AND D'ALMAINE	x-key tenoroon	London, 1785–1834
FT86	GRENSER, Augustin	4-key fagottino / octave	Dresden, ca. 1744–1798
FT15	GRENSER, Heinrich & WIESNER, Samuel	6-key fagottino / octave	Dresden, ca. 1824
FT16	GRENSER, Heinrich	5-key fagottino / octave	Dresden, ca. 1800
FT87	GRENSER, Heinrich	5-key fagottino / octave	Dresden, ca. 1800
FT50	GRENSER, Heinrich	6-key fagottino / octave	Dresden, ca. 1806–1813
M5	HAWKES & SON	12-key fagottino	London, 1923
M6	HAWKES & SON	12-key fagottino	London, 1925
FT88	HECKEL, Wilhelm	18-key tenoroon / F	Biebrich, 1907
FT41	HIRSBRUNNER (Gebrüder)	12-key tenoroon / F	Sumiswald, ca. 1830
FT89	HIRSBRUNNER (Gebrüder)	6-key tenoroon / F	Sumiswald, ca. 1815–1848
FT17	JACOBY Fils	5-key fagottino / octave	Auch, ca. 1785
FT90	KEY, Thomas	x-key fagottino	London, ca. 1805–1858
FT18	KRAUS, I.	4-key tenoroon / G	Germany, ca. 1750–1790
FT91	KRAUS, I.	3-key tenoroon / [G?]	Germany, ca. 1750–1790
FT92	KRAUS, I.	3-key tenoroon / [G?]	Germany, ca. 1750–1790
FT93	KRAUS, I.	4-key tenoroon / [G?]	Germany, ca. 1750–1790
FT94	KRAUS, I.	4-key tenoroon / [G?]	Germany, ca. 1750–1790
FT95	KÜSS, Wolfgang	9-key tenoroon	Vienna, ca. 1810–1839
FT49	KÜSS, Wolfgang	10-key tenoroon	Vienna, ca. 1810–1839
FT96	KÜSS, Wolfgang	9-key tenoroon	Vienna, ca. 1810–1840
FT59	KUTERUF, J.	3-key fagottino / octave	Germany, ca. 1700–1760
FT97	LE BRETON	Small-size bassoon referred as “counter-tenor basson”	Paris, ca. 1692
FT43	LEIBERZ, Johann Peter	7-key fagottino / octave	Koblenz, ca. 1825–1835
FT98	LOT, Martin	5-key fagottino / octave	Paris, ca. 1743–1785
FT99	LOT, Martin	3-key fagottino / octave	Paris, ca. 1743–1785
FT100	MAGVINI (MAGRINI)	8-key tenoroon / [F?]	Vienna, ca. 1800

FT37	MARZOLI, A.G. Philippe Tribert Marzoli Boehm (TMB)	15-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1865
M7	MEIKLE, William	8-key caledonica	Strathaven, 1825
FT19	MERKLEIN, I.	8-key tenoroon / F	Vienna, ca. 1835
FT57	MILHOUSE, William	4-key tenoroon / [G?]	London, ca. 1800
FT101	MILHOUSE, William	8-key tenoroon / G	London, ca. 1799–1828
FT102	MILHOUSE, William	6-key fagottino / octave	London, ca. 1800
M10	MILHOUSE, William and KEY, T.	8-key tenoroon	London, ca. 1795–1820
FT126	MORTON & SONS, Stamped JOHN PARR	x-key tenoroon	London, 1880–1890
FT103	MORTON, Alfred W.	15-key tenoroon / F	London, ca. 1870
FT20	MÜLLER	4-key fagottino / octave	Germany, ca. 1770
FT53	PACE, Charles	9-key tenoroon / F	London, ca. 1825
FT104	PEALE, T.	7-key tenoroon / [G?]	United Kingdom, ca. 1800– 1830
FT105	PELITTI	12-key tenoroon / F	Milan, ca. 1828–1870
M8	PIATET & BENOIT	x-key alto fagotto	Lyon, ca. 1850
FT21	PORTHAUX, Dominique A.	9-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1808
FT22	PROFF, François X.	5-key tenoroon / G	Tours, ca. 1800
FT106	PRUDENT [Thierriot]	x-key fagottino / octave	Paris, ca. 1765–1783
FT47	RIVA, Giacinto	13-key tenoroon / F	Ferrara, ca. 1860–1870
FT23	ROTTENBURGH, Godfrius A.	4-key fagottino / octave	Brussels, ca. 1760
FT107	ROTTENBURGH, Godfrius A.	x-fagottino / octave	Brussels, ca. 1760
FT108	ROTTENBURGH, Godfrius A.	x-key fagottino / octave	Brussels, ca. 1760
FT55	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	10-key fagottino / F	Paris, 1835
FT111	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	11-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1832
FT42	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	11-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1840
FT60	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	11-key tenoroon / G	Paris, 1824
FT110	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	12-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1843
FT26	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean- Nicholas	12-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1838

FT38	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	12-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1842
FT25	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	13-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1827
FT54	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	14-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1845–1850
FT109	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	14-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1840
FT112	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	15-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1840
FT113	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	15-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1835–1850
FT27	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	16-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1841
FT114	SAVARY JEUNE, Jean-Nicholas	x-key tenoroon / F	Paris, 1842
FT24	SAVARY PERE	5-key tenoroon / G	Paris, ca. 1810
FT58	SAXTON, Thomas	4-key tenoroon / G	Nottingham, ca. 1793–1799
FT28	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	4-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1760
FT29	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	4-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1764
FT44	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	4-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1760–1770
FT30	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	5-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1760–1778
FT39	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	4-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1750–1778
FT115	SCHERER, Johannes & Georg H.	4-key fagottino / octave	Butzbach, ca. 1750–1778
FT116	SCHLEGEL, Jeremias	4-key fagottino / octave	Basel, ca. 1752–1792
FT117	SCHOLL, Franz	x-key fagottino / octave	Vienna, 1803
FT118	SCHRAMME, C.	3-key fagottino / octave	Germany, ca. 1700–1740
FT5	SCHUBERT, Louis-Paul	13-key tenoroon / F	Paris, ca. 1860
FT119	SCHUSTER, Gottfried	6-key fagottino / octave	Markneukirchen, ca. 1820
FT120	SPADA, Gaetano	x-key tenoroon	Bologna, 1873
FT45	STEHLE, Johann	12-key tenoroon / F	Vienna, ca. 1850–1860
FT31	TAUBER, Kaspar	6-key tenoroon / [G?]	Vienna, ca. 1815
FT121	TAUBER, Kaspar	9-key tenoroon / F	Vienna, ca. 1798–1829
FT122	TAUBER, Kaspar	12-key tenoroon / F	Vienna, ca. 1798–1829
FT48	TAUBER, Kaspar	9-key tenoroon	Vienna, ca. 1798–1829

FT32	TÖLCKE, Heinrich Carl	4-key fagottino / octave	Braunschweig, ca. 1780
FT123	TÖLCKE, Heinrich Carl	4-key fagottino / octave	Braunschweig, ca. 1751–1835
FT124	TREUMANN	x-key tenoroon	Lyon, ca. 1825–1850
FT33	TUERLINCKX, Jean A.	4-key fagottino / octave	Mechelen, ca. 1795
FT34	TUERLINCKX, Jean A.	5-key tenoroon / F	Mechelen, ca. 1820
M2	WOOD, George	7-key alto fagotto	London, ca. 1835
M3	WOOD, George & IVY	8-key alto fagotto	London, ca. 1840
M9	[WOOD, George & IVY, unstamped]	7-key alto fagotto	London, ca. 1830
FT125	WUSSINGER, Franz	9-key tenoroon	Klagenfurt, ca. 1810–1841

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